

INFLUENCE OF SELF-ASSESSMENT CHARACTERISTICS ON SELF-EXPRESSION IN ADOLESCENCE

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Annotation. This article analyzes the effects of adolescent self-assessment on self-expression.

Keywords: self-delivery, self-expression, image, inner audience, image "I", perception, objective self-awareness.

Enter. Self-evaluation is little studied, and the theoretical main part of the research belongs to foreign scientists, such as I. Goffman, M. Snyder, R. Chaldini, I. Jones and T. Ittman. The concept of self-evaluation comes from the Latin word, which in translation means "self-delivery", that is, presenting yourself to other people. In the English annotated dictionary, it literally means managing one's own impressions through a myriad of behavioral strategies that involve presenting the appearance of others to other people.

In the American tradition, self-esteem is viewed in a slightly different way. It is interpreted as a form of social behavior demonstrated by the subject in the process of interpersonal communication. The most accurate definition of self-presentation belongs to J. Tedeschi and M. Riessom, in which self-presentation is described as intentional and conscious behavior that aims to make a unique impression among others. directed. Therefore, self-esteem is often synonymous with "self-presentation", "self-presentation", "impression management".¹

Self-assessment is defined as the ability to serve ourselves, to attract attention, by focusing on our qualities, which are carried out on the basis of the use of special technologies and strategies.

We face the phenomenon of self-assessment every day, often not knowing that a project of our own presentation has been formed in our subconscious mind. This type of presentation is usually called "natural self-presentation". But along with such a statement, this is not the only strategy of the individual. There is also a pre-planned, conscious tactic of placing a person, the so-called "artificial presentation". If the concept of "image" is focused on the creation of an image, that is, a certain stop line that determines the quality of the image subject, then

¹ Semenova L. N. self-presentation technology: educational and methodological complex / L. M. Semenova: Ed. Chelyabinsk: Yuurgudan. - 2005. Page 38

self-representation is the dynamics of self-delivery in the process of demonstrating these qualities.

Self-presentation refers to a person's desire to present the desired image for an external audience (for other people) and an internal audience (for himself). Not intentionally or unintentionally, people defend themselves to assert their "i-image". In familiar situations, this occurs without conscious effort, and in unfamiliar situations, consciously.

E. L. Dotsenko analyzes the image management process as a type of manipulation.² Other researchers consider self-presentation to be a process of managing attention by engaging special mechanisms of social perception related to the subject's appearance. Yu. M. Zhukov considers self-presentation to be a system of effective communication rules.³

The above theories (situational theories) focus on external factors of self-presentation. But there are also theories that are crucial to the internal factors of self-feeding (motivational theories). There are also a number of theories that try to take into account the external and internal factors of self-esteem.

Another line of research refers to the study of individual differences and tendencies in the process of self-evaluation. One of the first works in this direction was carried out by R. A. Wikland, who associated the subject's mind with a special state of self-directed attention, which he called "objective self-called "self-awareness". Wickland's theory has spawned a number of studies that have focused on the relationship between "objective self-awareness" and "behavioral action."

A. Fenigstein, M. Sherif and A. Bass began to consider "self-awareness" as a source of personal characteristics (self-awareness scale) and identified the following aspects of understanding:

- a) Self-awareness of the person (pays attention to his true feelings),
- b) Self-awareness in the community (related to self-interest as a social object),
- c) Social anxiety (this reflects the nature of a person's loss due to social attention).⁴

For the first time, the problem of controlling one's own impression appears in the works of I. Hoffmann, who developed the concept of "social dramaturgy". Its essence is that in the process of social interaction, a person can look at

² Dotsenko E. L. The psychology of manipulation: phenomena, mechanisms and protection / E. L. Dotsenko. M.: Che.Ro: Yurayt, 2000. Page 263

³ Zhukov Yu. m. efficiency of business relations / yu. M. Zhukov. - M.: Knowledge, 1988. Page 23.

⁴ Semenov I. N. self-management of the individual as a subject of vital activity / I. N. Semenov // fundamentals of general and applied acmeology. - M.: Science, 1995. Pages 86-87.

himself through the eyes of a partner and adjust his behavior in accordance with the wishes of others, create the most favorable impression of himself, this interaction able to get the most out of the secret.⁵

Interesting developments of the problem of self-awareness are presented in the works of D. Myers, most people believe that they have exaggerated self-awareness and they expect a positive attitude towards them from those around them, which may not always be justified in reality .⁶

Self-awareness can be considered a set of self-centered relationships. This relationship includes:

- 1) a person's belief, which may be justified or unjustified, forms the cognitive level of self-presentation;
- 2) the emotional reaction to this belief forms the emotional evaluative level of self-expression;
- 3) the appropriate reaction expressed in actions forms the behavioral level of self-awareness.

In relation to self-awareness, these aspects can be defined as follows.

- 1) Self-image - a person's idea about himself;
- 2) Self-awareness is an affective evaluation of the image, which can have different intensity, because the characteristics of the image are more or less strong feeling related to their acceptance or judgment - can cause emotions;
- 3) behavioral response, i.e., self-image is a result of self-awareness.

Self-awareness can be considered a three-step process that is interrelated. The cognitive level of self-presentation is based on the image subject's ideas about himself. At the same time, the subject always exaggerates his importance, his idea of himself is based on objective knowledge or subjective opinion. This level of self-presentation is related to self-awareness of its positive and negative characteristics, stable trends of behavior, clarity of perception.

At the approximate level of self-awareness, we are connected with the realization that the quality that we attribute to our own personality is not always objective, and that other people are not always ready to agree with them. Only age, sex, height, profession and other information that has sufficient contention will not lead to disagreements. There is a strong moment of self-evaluation in attempts to describe oneself. The source of ideas about self-evaluation is the social environment and social reactions to its manifestation.

⁵ Hoffman Irving introducing oneself to others in everyday life / Irving Hoffman: translated from English. A. D. Kovaleva: Institute of Sociology of the Russian Academy of Sciences. - M.: Canon-press-Ts: Kuchkovo-pole, 2000. 302 p.

⁶ Chernyaev G. V. presentation of the person / G. V. Chernyaeva. - M.: Max Press, 2002. Page 56.

That being said, the new social assessment could change the picture. Thus, self-evaluation reflects the level of development of the subject's sense of self-worth, a sense of self-worth, and a positive attitude towards everything that falls within his sphere. Therefore, to increase the level of self-esteem of the subject of the image, you can use the self-hypnosis method, which is similar to the hymn "I am loved" and can lower self-esteem. Self-evaluation is manifested in the conscious judgments of the subject, in which he tries to form his own importance. For this, we focus on the following three points:

- 1) comparing the image of the real self with the image of the ideal self, which forms the idea of how a person wants to be;
- 2) in order to form self-evaluation, it is necessary to direct the social attitude towards oneself to internal feelings, that is, to evaluate oneself in a way that is evaluated by others;
- 3) the subject evaluates the success of his actions and manifestations through the object of his identity and is satisfied with what "fits" with the greatest success into the composition of society.

Self-evaluation is related to the achievement of the behavioral outcome and is the act of self-evaluation itself. There are concepts and other ideas that emphasize that a person always follows the path of achieving maximum internal consistency. These are the ideas, feelings, ideas of the subject that are in conflict with feelings, ideas, do not harmonize the personality, and cause psychological discomfort. In order to restore the lost state of internal harmony, the subject is ready for various actions: it is necessary to refuse to see things as they are, to try to change oneself and others in some way. One of these mechanisms is rationalization. This mechanism was proved by F. J. Rogers, who uses one of the defense mechanisms that respond to the threat of dissonance - violation or rejection.⁷

Distortion is used to change the personal significance of an experience, and denial, as it were, destroys the existence of the experience. Internal contradictions often become a source of stress, because they are characterized by the ability to realistically assess the situation.

Self-evaluation as a me, as a high level of self-awareness, are important moments of prevention and deviant behavior, crisis situations, to solve the problems of self-determination. are important factors that help, It is relevant in the period of adolescence, in the experimental study we conducted, 15 and 5 high school students in the city of Ko'kan, 14-16-year-old adolescents, a total of

⁷ Rogers F. J. The way to success: how the corporation works / F. J. Rogers. - where is it? Translated from English. - St. Petersburg.: ABC-Terra, 1997. Page 147|

100 people participated did 57 students of the 9th grade (29 boys and 28 girls), 43 students of the 10th grade (27 girls and 16 boys) were transferred.

The study was conducted in September-October 2022, based on theoretical data on self-esteem problems in adolescent children, and the general and specific self-esteem of 10th graders. It was hypothesized that self-assessment should be characterized by greater reflexivity based on deeper self-awareness than 9th graders.

3 methods were used in the research process:

1. Methodology of studying self-relationship (Pantelev, Stolin).
2. I used the Dembo-Rubinstein technique.
3. Method A "incomplete sentences" (option Sachs a and Levy).

According to the Pantileev methodology, the characteristics of the self-assessment attitude are analyzed according to 9 dimensions (closeness, self-confidence, self-control, reflected self self-attitude, self-esteem, self-acceptance, self-attachment, internal conflict, self-blame).

Each scale is evaluated according to the given scale.

Self-evaluation attitude	9th grade	10th grade
Proximity	Average 40%	Average 50%
Self confidence	Average 50%	Average 60%
Self-management	Changeable	Changeable
Reflected self-relation	The highest 70%	The highest 80%
Self-esteem	The highest 70%	The highest 80%
Self-acceptance	The highest 60%	The highest 80%
Self-subordination	The highest 60%	The highest 70%
Internal conflict	The lowest 40%	The lowest 50%
Self-blame	The lowest 50%	The lowest 50%

Conclusion. From this, we can talk about the fact that adolescents are not formed. In 9th grade students, we can say that an open attitude towards oneself and, as a result, the cognitive component of self-awareness and the self are not formed enough for me.

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